

CONTENT ANALYSIS OF THE ASSORTMENT OF NON-STEROIDAL ANTI- INFLAMMATORY DRUGS

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Relevance: inflammatory processes represent one of the primary pathogenetic factors in the development of numerous diseases. Therefore, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are widely used in clinical practice due to their significant role in alleviating pain, reducing body temperature, and suppressing inflammation. Globally, NSAIDs are among the most commonly used medications, with millions of patients relying on them, making this group of drugs one of the most in-demand in the global pharmaceutical market. Despite the high demand for NSAIDs in the pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan, a significant proportion of these drugs are imported from foreign manufacturers. This leads to increased dependency on imports and restricts the potential of domestic pharmaceutical producers. In the context of ongoing reforms aimed at developing the pharmaceutical industry in Uzbekistan, expanding the range of domestically produced medicines, increasing the share of local manufacturers, and producing high-quality and affordable drugs that meet market demands are considered urgent priorities. From this perspective, the study of the NSAID assortment, dosage forms, and distribution by manufacturers holds both scientific and practical importance.

Purpose of the study: to conduct a content analysis of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs registered in the State Register between 2020 and 2024, determine their assortment, dosage forms, and distribution by manufacturers, identify existing challenges, and outline prospective directions for development.

Materials and methods: the research was based on data from the State Register of Medicines of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The content analysis method was applied to study the number of NSAIDs registered from 2020 to 2024, their distribution by manufacturing countries, and the proportion of various dosage forms. In addition, the drugs were categorized based on their active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs). The results were evaluated through statistical analysis and comparative assessment.

Results: according to the obtained data, in 2024, NSAIDs constituted 1.34% (128 drugs) of the total number of registered medicines. Among the dosage forms, suspensions accounted for 27%, solutions 20%, suppositories 15%, tablets 9%, gels 7%, ointments and capsules 5% each, creams 3%, syrups and granules 2% each, and eye drops made up 5%. The analysis revealed that the majority of soft dosage forms were produced by foreign (63%) and CIS (21%) manufacturers, whereas the share of local manufacturers was only 16%. Between 2020 and 2024, the total NSAID assortment decreased from 177 to 124. During this period, the share of domestic manufacturers fell from 27% to 17%, and the share of CIS countries declined from 23% to 11%. Foreign manufacturers maintained their leading position with a market share of 49%. The most frequently used active ingredients were diclofenac, ibuprofen, and indomethacin, indicating a narrow dependency on a limited range of APIs in the market.

Conclusions: the findings indicate that the share of local pharmaceutical enterprises in the production of NSAIDs remains insufficient. The heavy reliance on imported soft dosage forms makes the domestic market dependent on foreign products. In order to advance the local pharmaceutical industry, it is essential to expand NSAID production, introduce new dosage forms through innovative technologies, and utilize medicinal plant-based raw materials. Furthermore, strengthening collaboration with international pharmaceutical companies, adopting modern manufacturing technologies, and supporting scientific research activities of local manufacturers will contribute significantly to progress in this area.